

Kinetics and Mechanism of Anation of Hydroxopentaaquo-chromium(III) Ion by DL-Methionine in Water—Ethanol Medium

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The kinetics of substitution of aquo-ligands of hydroxopentaaquochromium(III) ion by DL-methionine in water—ethanol medium has been studied spectrophotometrically. The rate law involving the ion-pair formation has been established as

$$\frac{d[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5(\text{OH})(\text{Methio})_2]}{dt} = \frac{k_a K_E [\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5(\text{OH})]_{\text{total}}^2 [\text{Methio. II}]}{1 + K_E [\text{Methio. H}]}$$

where, k_a is the anation rate constant, K_E is the ion-pair equilibrium constant and $[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5(\text{OH})]_{\text{total}}^2$ is the concentration of the total amount of unreacted substrate and $[\text{Methio. H}]$ is the concentration of zwitterionic methionine. The reaction rate is higher compared to the rates of water-exchange and other anation reactions of hydroxopentaaquochromium(III) ion. Activation parameters have been calculated and compared with other substitution reactions of the same complex. Mechanism involving the prior formation of ion-pair followed by associative interchange (I_a) has been suggested.

ANATION reaction of hexaaquochromium(III) ion have been studied extensively¹⁻³ and different mechanisms have been proposed. Study with hydroxopentaaquochromium(III) ion has not received similar attention. Recently, such reactions have been studied in our laboratory⁴⁻¹². Hydroxide ion plays an important role by virtue of its σ - as well as π -bonding ability.

Despite of large amount of work done on chromium(III) complexes the controversy regarding its mechanism persists^{2,3}. Furthermore, aquo-ligand substitution in hydroxopentaaquochromium(III) ion by amino acids containing sulphur donors has not been studied so far. We planned to study the substitution kinetics of the aquo-ligands of $\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5(\text{OH})^{2+}$ by amino acids and amino acids containing sulphur donor, like histidine, methionine, cysteine, pencillamine, hydroxyproline *etc.* in water—ethanol mixture with the hope that these studies will enlighten this area. Here, we report the results of anation of $\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5(\text{OH})^{2+}$ by DL-methionine—a thio amino acid.

Experimental

$[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6][\text{ClO}_4]_3$ was prepared¹³ using A.R. grade chemicals. Hydroxopentaaquochromium(III) (Complex-I) was prepared *in situ* from the hexaaquo-complex by adjusting the pH to 5. Complex-I showed absorption maxima at 430 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 1.447) and 590 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 1.255) quite different from those of hexaaquochromium(III) ion. The

product of the reaction between $[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5(\text{OH})]^{2+}$ and DL-methionine was prepared by mixing them in different molar ratio, (*viz.* 1 : 1, 1 : 2, 1 : 3) and thermostated at 50° for 48 h. The absorption spectra of 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 mixtures exhibited the same spectra having maximum absorption at 400 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 1.74) and 540 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 1.75) (quite different from that of Complex-I). However, the absorbance of 1 : 1 mixture was lower at the absorption maxima due to the presence of excess of Complex-I concentration.

Elemental analyses revealed that highly soluble maroon coloured crystalline product possessed the composition $[\text{Cr}(\text{Methio})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{OH})]$ (Complex-II). The solution of the Complex-II remained unabsorbed by cationic and anionic ion-exchangers. The composition was also checked by Job's method of continuous variation. The ir spectra of the isolated solid product (Complex-II) was taken by a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer for further verification of the composition of the product. The broad and strong band around 3 300–3 600 cm^{-1} indicated simple OH stretching vibration or OH in water or both. The OH stretching vibration of carboxylic acid group at 2 600–3 100 cm^{-1} (in ligand) was found to be absent in the Complex-II, indicating the participation of the carboxyl group during complexation; also proved by the absence of O–H bending band at 1 280 cm^{-1} but the presence of M–O bending band at 950 cm^{-1} . The C–S bending band at 1 150 cm^{-1} was present in the spectra of

the ligand as well as the metal complex, indicating sulphur atom not functioning as a donor centre.

All the kinetic runs were followed by measuring absorbance at 540 nm using a Hilger UVISPEK spectrophotometer. It was found that a substantial difference existed in the spectra of Complex-I and Complex-II. Equal volume of solution of ligand methionine and Complex-I were mixed, pH was adjusted and then thermostated at a particular temperature in reaction vessels. The composition of the reaction mixture was such that the first order rate law be applicable. The pseudo-first order rate constants for the substitution reaction were obtained by plotting $\log (D_\infty - D_0 / D_\infty - D_t)$ against time, D_∞ , D_0 and D_t being the absorbances at the completion of the reaction at the beginning of the reaction and after time t , respectively; and the rate constant values being reproducible within $\pm 3\%$.

Results and Discussion

Effect of [Complex-I] on rate constant : At a fixed [Methio.H] 0.05 M, ionic strength (μ) 0.01 and pH 5, [Complex-I] was varied. It was observed that the rate constants were 19.6×10^{-5} , 19.56×10^{-5} and $19.61 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for [Complex-I] 0.002, 0.0025 and 0.0040 mol dm⁻³, respectively, at 308 K. Thus the rate of reaction was first order with respect to [Complex-I],

$$\frac{d[\text{Complex-II}]}{dt} = k[\text{Complex-I}]$$

Effect of pH on rate constant : At fixed [Complex-I] (0.0025 M), [Methionine] (0.025 M) and $\mu = 0.0075 \text{ M}$, the values of the pseudo-first order rate constants ($k_{\text{obs}} \times 10^5$) at 308 K were 6.39, 8.00, 11.23, 13.5 and 16.63 s⁻¹ at pH 4.5, 4.8, 5.0, 5.2 and 5.3, respectively, (Fig. 1A) (pH adjusted by adding NaOH or HClO₄).

Fig. 1 A. Plot of $\log (D_\infty - D_0 / D_\infty - D_t)$ vs time at 35° and different pH: (A) 4.46, (B) 4.8, (C) 5.0, (D) 5.21, and (E) 5.31. [Complex-I] = 0.0025 M, [Methio.H] = 0.025 M.

B. Plot of $\log (D_\infty - D_0 / D_\infty - D_t)$ vs time at 35° in different medium: (A) perchlorate medium, and (B) nitrate medium, [Complex-I] = 0.0025 M, [Methio.H] = 0.05 M, pH = 5.0, $\mu = 0.9 \text{ M}$.

The value of pK_1 (isoionic point) = 5.7. So in the above mentioned pH range, it is understandable from the two acid dissociation equilibrium, that mainly the zwitterionic form of the ligand exists in solution. So in the pH range 4.5–5.3, the nature of the ligand remains unaltered. However, the increase of rate with pH may be explained considering the acid dissociation equilibrium,

It is clear that at pH 3.8, the percentage of hexaquo species and the hydroxopentaaquo species is approximately the same at the experimental temperature. But the increase in pH increases the percentage of the more reactive hydroxopentaaquo species. The enhanced reactivity of the hydroxopentaaquo species is due to labilising effect of hydroxide ion adjacent to the water molecule by

virtue of its lone-pair of electrons capable of exerting strong electromeric effect. Hydroxide ion is also a strong π -donor which facilitates the formation of very reactive hydroxo-intermediate and hence increases the rate.

Effect of [Methionine] on rate constant: Maintaining at a constant [Complex-I] (0.0025 M), ionic strength 0.0075 M and pH 5.0, the concentration of the ligand was varied in the range 0.0125–0.05 M. The values of k_{obs} obtained are presented in Table 1. It is observed that the rate of reaction increased with the increase in ligand concentration,

TABLE 1—VARIATION OF RATE CONSTANT WITH [Methio.H] AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

pH=5.0, $\mu=0.0075 M$

[Ligand] M	$k_{obs} (\times 10^5 s^{-1})$			
	35°	40°	45°	50°
0.0125	5.90	10.51	15.00	—
0.01875	9.97	15.50	26.20	30.60
0.0250	11.23	18.04	32.87	40.30
0.03125	—	—	—	46.01
0.0375	16.95	26.28	47.00	56.03
0.0500	19.56	33.42	51.70	67.11

but at a high [Ligand] a limiting rate is reached as shown in Fig. 2A. This may be explained due to

Fig 2 A. Variation of k_{obs} with [Methio.H] at different temperature: (A) 35°, (B) 40°, (C) 45°, and (D) 50°; [Complex-I]=0.025 M, pH=5.0.

B. Plot of $1/k_{obs}$ vs $1/[Methio.H]$ at different temperature.

the completion on ion-pair formation¹⁴. The following reaction scheme can be suggested to explain such variation of reaction rate with ligand concentration

On the basis of the above scheme, considering the ion-pair equilibrium and rate determining step, the following rate law has been established,

$$\frac{d[\text{Complex-II}]}{dt} = \frac{k_a K_E [Cr(H_2O)_5(OH)]_{total}^{2+} [Methio.H]}{1 + K_E [Methio.H]}$$

$$= k_{obs} [Cr(H_2O)_5(OH)]_{total}^{2+}$$

[Cr(H₂O)₅(OH)²⁺]_{total} = Concentration of total amount unreacted [Complex-I] in solution

Therefore,

$$k_{obs} = \frac{k_a K_E [Methio.H]}{1 + K_E [Methio.H]}$$

Hence, $1/k_{obs} = 1/k_a + 1/k_a K_E [Methio.H]$

where, K_E is ion pair equilibrium constant and k_a the rate constant for interchange of outersphere complex to innersphere complex. So the plot of $1/k_{obs}$ vs $1/[L]$ should be linear with intercept of $1/k_a$ and slope $1/k_a K_E$. This is found to be so as shown the Fig. 2B. The values of $k_{anation}$ and K_E are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—VALUES OF INTERCHANGE RATE CONSTANT (k_a) AND ION-PAIR EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANT (K_E) FOR ANATION BY DL-METHIONINE AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Temp. K	k_a $\times 10^4 s^{-1}$	K_E $dm^3 mol^{-1}$
308	8.0	6.0
313	13.0	7.1
318	20.2	8.1
323	28.01	8.8

Rate of anation is much faster than that of isotopic water exchange^{15,16} at common temperature indicating associative character of the interchange process, i.e. bond formation by the incoming ligand plays a significant role in the interchange step. Comparing the data obtained from literature^{2,9-12,15,16} for the anation of $Cr(H_2O)_5(OH)^{2+}$ with other ligands, it is found that the rate constants show significant dependence on the nature

of the incoming ligand. It may be assumed that the anation reaction takes place through the associative interchange mechanism.

Influence of ionic strength on reaction rate : The ionic strength of the reaction mixture was changed by the addition of sodium perchlorate at fixed [Complex-I] (0.0025 M), [Ligand] (0.05 M) and pH 5.0. It was observed that the pseudo-first order rate constants were 1.9×10^{-4} , 1.92×10^{-4} , 1.91×10^{-4} s^{-1} for $\mu = 0.11$, 0.24 and 0.303 M, respectively, i.e. rate of reaction is unchanged in different ionic strength of the solution. Considering the net charge of methionine (in zwitterionic form) being zero, the results obtained is supported by the theory proposed by Bronsted, Bjerrum and others¹⁹. But if the ionic strength of the medium is altered by adding $NaNO_3$, the rate of reaction is increased. At fixed [Complex-I] (0.0025 M), [Methionine] (0.05 M), pH (5.0), temperature (308 K) and ionic strength (0.3 M, adjusted by adding $NaNO_3$), it was found that the rate of reaction was 3.24×10^{-4} s^{-1} (Fig. 1B). It may be due to the fact that non-substituting nitrate ion facilitates metal-water bond fission through specific attack on the coordinated water molecule. Consequently, labilisation of water molecules catalyses the entry of dipolar methionine, and hence the increase in rate is observed. This typical ionic strength effect was also observed by Brown and Harris²⁰. Similar nitrate-ion-induced rate acceleration was observed by Ghosh and Banerjee²¹ in the anation of $cis-Co(NH_3)_4(H_2O)_2^{3+}$ by SCN^- and N_3^- ions. They assumed that the aqua-ligand is pulled off by nitrate ion facilitating the entry of the substituting anion. Van Eldik²² also observed nitrate-ion-promoted anation and they proposed a model in which there is interaction of nitrate with two aquo-ligands in *cis*-positions.

Effect of temperature on reaction rate : The reaction rate was followed at four different temperature for different [Ligand] to find out the effect of temperature on the values of rate constants for interchange process. The results are given in Table 2.

Activation parameters were calculated from the linear Eyring plot of $\log k_a$ vs $1/T$. A lower $\Delta H^\ddagger$ (59.8 $kJ\ mol^{-1}$) and a large negative $\Delta S^\ddagger$ (-97 $J\ K\ mol^{-1}$) compared to isotopic water-exchange were obtained. This lower value of $\Delta H^\ddagger$ suggests significant incoming ligand participation in the transition state. Further, the activated complex formation through outer-sphere association is stabilised by hydrogen bonding between the water molecule of the inner-sphere complex and the negative end of methionine dipole. This led to the formation of a stable and compact activated state as evidenced from the large negative $\Delta S^\ddagger$ value. The above facts indicate that the reaction occurs through an associative interchange process. Similar results were obtained in other systems^{9-12,17}. The associative interchange mechanism for the present

system is further supported by the isokinetic plot¹⁸ of $\Delta H^\ddagger$ vs $\Delta S^\ddagger$ (Fig. 3) of similar systems; a straight line being obtained with a slope = 308.4, within the experimental temperature range.

Fig. 3. Isokinetic plot of different systems: (1) DL-alanine, (2) glycine, (3) aspartic acid, (4) β -alanine, and (5) methionine.

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